

Synthesis of *pp'*-Diphenylenedimonosulphide.

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p-Phenylenedimercaptan gives on oxidation a white amorphous powder possessing the empirical formula $(C_6H_4S_2)_n$. As the disulphide (or polysulphide?) so formed is insoluble in all organic solvents it has not been possible yet to solve by determining its molecular weight the question as to what is the nature of complexity of the molecule. It was thought worth while to try the action of some suitable desulphurising agents upon the di-(or poly?) sulphide with the hope that the desulphurised product would be an aromatic hydrocarbon (I), (II) or (III) and which in all probability would be soluble in organic solvents and would lend itself to molecular weight determination.

In order to remove the sulphur atoms, desulphurising agents such as sodium, molecular sodium, mercury, mercuric chloride and nitrate, *natur cupfer* and freshly reduced copper have been tried under varying conditions of experiments. Of all these reagents *natur cupfer* and freshly reduced copper have only been found to be suitable for the purpose and the product isolated from the reaction

(*Annalen*, 1907, 351, 151) which according to recent work (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, *Chemical Reviews*, 1933, 12, 269) has been definitely proved to be wrong. The fact that diphenyl has been proved to possess an extended co-planar structure and that attempts to convert its *pp'*-diiodo derivative into *pp'*-diphenylene have resulted in failure (Sircar and De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 245) do not necessarily mean that a substance like diphenylenedimonosulphide should be incapable of existence. In diphenyl two nuclear carbon atoms are directly connected and in the other the two pairs of *para* carbon atoms are connected through sulphur, which must exert some sort of effect on the valency directions in consequence of which the two pair of *para*-carbon atoms might come sufficiently near to be linked through sulphur. The phenylene residues in compound $C_{12}H_8S_2$ can be in one plane as shown in A or in a plane perpendicular or inclined at some angle to that of the paper as shown in B. Substitution products of this

(A)

(B)

interesting compound might lend themselves to optical resolution due to the asymmetry of the molecule as a whole. Model B even with one substituent will make the molecule asymmetric; whereas there is the possibility of substituents making model A assume an asymmetric structure due to restricted rotation on the basis of which the optical activity of the diphenyl derivatives is now explained (*Chem. Ind.*, 1926, 45, 831, 864, 884). The effect of other groups like $(CH_2)_n$, CO and $(NH)_n$ in bridge formation between two pairs of *para* carbon atoms of two benzene molecules is under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Phenylenedisulphochloride was prepared starting from sulphanic acid via potassium xanthosulphonate of benzene ($KO_3S \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot S \cdot CS \cdot OEt$) and potassium benzene disulphonate. The disul-

phochloride melted at 139° and not at 131° as given by Koerner and Monslise (*Gazzetta*, 1876, 6, 140), Jackson and Wing (*Am. Chem. J.*, 1887, 9, 332) give 139°, Zincke and Frohneberg (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2721) give 138°.

p-Phenylenedimercaptan.—(a) The method of Sestini (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 584) for reduction of the sulphochloride by means of tin and hydrochloric acid was found not to give more than 20 % of theoretical yield.

(b) Reduction of the sulphochloride (1 mol.) by means of hydrochloric acid (13 mols.) and zinc dust (6.5 mols.) added portion-wise under reflux did not give more than 25 % yield.

(c) The method given in "Organic Synthesis", Vol. I, p. 71 (for the preparation of thiophenol) was also tried with the result that the yield could only be raised up to 30 % of theory.

(d) *The best method.*—An intimate mixture of the disulphochloride (31 g.) and zinc dust (100 g.) was suspended in water (150 c. c.) in a three-necked round bottomed flask (1 litre capacity) fitted with a long upright condenser. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (300 c.c.) was then added drop by drop during half an hour from a separating funnel while the mixture was stirred by a mercury-sealed stirrer. (It was found that the commercial hydrochloric acid gave a better yield than when Merck's pure hydrochloric acid was used.) The stirring was continued for half an hour after addition of the acid was over. The flask was then heated gently for about an hour and then vigorously with the addition of some more zinc (20 g.) and hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.); rapidly cooled in ice-water and the contents filtered. The white precipitate was digested with absolute alcohol thrice and the small quantity of insoluble residue was again treated with zinc dust (20 g.), hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.) and water, boiled, cooled as before and extracted with absolute alcohol. The concentrated alcoholic extracts on being poured into an excess of water gave the mercaptan as a white precipitate. It crystallised from 95 % alcohol, m. p. 96-97° which rose to 98° on recrystallisation; yield, 12 g. (75 % of theory).

Oxidation of the dimercaptan has been effected by Lustig (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1890, ii, 41, 206) and also by Frohnsberg (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2727) by various oxidising agents. We found it more convenient, however, to adopt the following method:

Ferric chloride (120 g.) dissolved in hot alcohol (150 c.c.) was added to the mercaptan (15 g.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot alcohol when a yellowish precipitate was formed. The reaction mixture was heated for about two minutes more, filtered hot, washed several times with hot alcohol under suction and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It is an amorphous powder insoluble in organic solvents and not melting even at 300°. (Found: S, 45·93. $(C_6H_4S_2)_n$ requires S, 45·71 per cent).

Desulphurisation with reduced copper in a current of carbon dioxide.—A narrow hard glass tube (18" long), sealed at one end, was charged with powdered magnesite (2") followed by an intimate mixture of the polysulphide (4 g.) and freshly reduced copper (10 g.) and then a column of reduced copper (2") with asbestos plugs separating them. The open end of the tube was bent at an angle of about 120° drawn narrower and immersed under water contained in a beaker. The burner below magnesite was first ignited and a slow current of carbon dioxide allowed to bubble through water, the burners below the copper powder and the substance were lighted gradually and the heating continued for 3 hours when a few drops of an oil collected on the surface of water. The ethereal extract of the oil was dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and yielded after distilling off the ether a thick oily substance which contained sulphur. The ether and benzene extracts of the contents of the tube gave only a very small quantity of tarry mass which could not be purified. The metallic residue evolved hydrogen sulphide profusely on treatment with hydrochloric acid.

A modified process.— An intimate mixture of the polysulphide (7·5 g.) and reduced copper (15 g.) was heated in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a vertical tube at its mouth and carrying a calcium chloride guard tube at the end for 2, 6 and 12 hours at 200°, 250° and 300° in a metal bath, making altogether nine experiments. It was only in the last experiment that some reaction was found to take place. The extracts of the contents of the flask in hot dry benzene yielded a small quantity of a brownish-yellow heavy oil. From six such experiments only 0·9 g. of the thick oil could be collected. Attempts at its purification failed due to its extreme solubility in all organic solvents. Some crystals, however, separated from the oil on standing in a vacuum desiccator for about two months which were carefully separated by filtration under suction and then washed with dry benzene, m. p. 146-47°; after crystallisation from benzene

the m. p. rose to 148° , on recrystallisation the m.p. remained unchanged. The substance was recovered unchanged after being boiled with zinc and hydrochloric acid and did not contain any mercaptan. [Found: (micro* method) C, 67.94; H, 3.99; S, 28.84, M. W., 216. $C_{12}H_8S_2$ requires C, 66.66; H, 3.7; S, 29.62 per cent. M. W., 216).

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* 0.024 G. of the substance was sent to Prof. Pregl of the University of Graz in December 1930 for micro analysis and molecular weight determinations and these results have been communicated to us by Dr. August Verdino, the lamentable death of Prof. Pregl having occurred in the meantime.